

Hidden Hunger in Adolescent Obesity: Micronutrient Deficiencies and the Neglect of Male Adolescents

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Abstract

Adolescent obesity is increasingly classified as a paradoxical form of malnutrition where an excessive caloric intake exists alongside clinically significant micronutrient deficiencies that are commonly referred to as hidden hunger. This scoping review aims to summarize all of the evidence found from 2021-2026 related to micronutrient deficiencies found in adolescents with obesity while emphasizing both the lack of representation for male adolescents as well as all the other populations considered underrepresented in the literature such as adolescent athletes, and adolescents who have undergone surgery for weight loss (bariatric). The articles included in this review were obtained via various databases including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar and ScienceDirect, using pre-established search terms and keywords related to nutrition and obesity.

The findings from the studies included in this review indicate that adolescents with obesity continue to suffer from deficiencies in vitamin D, iron, zinc, folate, vitamin B12 and other micronutrients despite consuming excessive calories. Major contributing factors to these deficiencies are poor quality diets, high consumption of ultra-processed foods, chronic low-grade inflammation, altered metabolism of micronutrients, and a lack of physical activity/sedentary lifestyle. In addition, findings from this review indicate that males are currently underrepresented in the nutritional research and assessment of adolescents and as a result, the data collected on this population is insufficient. Overall, findings from this review indicate that improved assessment and screening of micronutrients and improved surveillance of adolescent nutrition is necessary in order to address the issue of hidden hunger in adolescents who are obese and the long-term metabolic and developmental consequences associated with this condition.

Keywords: Adolescent obesity; Hidden hunger; Micronutrient deficiencies; Male adolescents; Sex-disaggregated nutrition research

Introduction

Adolescent years are important for development and growth, with increased energy and nutritional needs, including 'hidden' nutritional crises for adolescents [1]. The onset of puberty induces a spur in growth rate and therefore affects nutritional needs for macro and micro nutrients in dietary intake. Adolescent needs for calories, protein, iron, calcium, zinc and folate increase during rapid linear growth of the skeleton and ossification of bone [2]. During adolescence the individual grows considerably, with about 45% of bone mass obtained during this stage, also there is growth of soft tissue, size of organs and quantity of red blood cells [3]. This period of dramatic but positive physical changes and development, includes changes to body composition, fluctuation of metabolism and hormonal secretion, maturation of physiologic systems, and establishment of nutrient reserves, may adversely affect future health [4]. The adolescent population has increased risks for poor nutrition, despite the fact that adolescents have been shown to consume increasingly poor-quality diets throughout their adolescent years [5].

In 2025, for the first time, there were more school-age children and adolescents with obesity globally than underweight. The complete reversal of the traditional 'malnutrition' pattern, which is occurring worldwide, threatens the future health and development of children, families and countries [6]. Low- and middle-income countries, especially, are experiencing the double burden of malnutrition due to rapid transition to better nutritional habits resulting from increasing economic growth, urbanisation, globalisation and technological advances [7]. The increasing role of high socio-economic status as the primary cause of obesity in adolescents is primarily due to the more sedentary lifestyle of young people related to higher usage of media and increased exposure to lower quality nutritional food advertising [8].

Obesity is a paradox of malnutrition where excessive energy intake is related to inadequate individual micronutrient intakes [9]. "Hidden Hunger" describes the condition of having a number of micronutrient deficiencies while being on an energy-surplus diet [10]. Iron, zinc, iodine and vitamin A are considered to be the four most common limiting micronutrients (i.e., micronutrients which limit the quality of diet), which may occur due to the consumption of the energy-dense but nutritionally poor-quality food [11]. About 2 billion people globally are estimated to experience hidden hunger, mainly from low- or middle-income countries where

people consume inexpensive staple foods and have monotonous diets from limited choices due to poverty [10]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), malnutrition is the greatest public health threat in the world; this condition will be present in 20-60% of patients in hospitals [12]. The state of malnutrition in obesity is an active, pathological process as a result of the interaction of diet quality, systemic inflammation, and metabolic dysfunction [13].

Identifying gender differences in pediatric nutrition is essential for creating effective nutrition strategies or programs in children with obesity, and other diseases [14]. Disaggregating sex, or grouping boys and girls separately from older adolescents (age 19–24) is a dramatic shortcoming to identify those populations in East Asia and the Pacific (EAP) and Europe and Central Asia (ECA), as well as within low- and medium-income countries (LMICs) to disaggregate by locality of residence (urban/rural) [15]. This review is also overall motivating by why is there a paradox of hidden hunger within adolescent obesity with excessive energy intake along with significant clinical micronutrient deficiencies. There is a major limitation in evidence that is disaggregated by sex; it is very uncommon to profile male adolescents due to their biological and behavioral vulnerabilities. This review includes discussion of two additional underrepresented at-risk groups of adolescents, athletes and those who have undergone bariatric surgery.

Methodology

This study was conducted as a scoping review to synthesize current evidence on micronutrient deficiencies in adolescents with obesity, with particular emphasis on the underrepresentation of male adolescents in nutritional research. This review has also included an exploration of populations of adolescents that remain understudied, including those participating in athletics and adolescents who have undergone or will undergo bariatric (surgical) procedures. To perform the scientific literature search, the authors searched multiple databases (i.e., PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, ScienceDirect) for articles published between January 2021 and May 2026. The search results were obtained by searching through a variety of different combinations of terms using Boolean operators, and included terms such as: adolescent obesity, hidden hunger, micronutrient deficiency, male adolescents, vitamin D deficiency, iron deficiency, zinc, folate, vitamin B12, overnutrition, sex-disaggregated nutrition, and adolescent nutrition. The authors included many different types of articles in their review including systematic reviews, meta-analyses, cohort and cross-sectional studies, randomized controlled trials, narrative reviews, and public health surveillance reports

published in English. Articles were included if they provided data on any of the following: micronutrient status; dietary quality; obesity-related metabolic dysfunction; or sex-specific nutritional vulnerabilities among male and female adolescents aged 10 – 19 years. Articles that were focused only on adults; pregnant women; severe chronic illness that is not related to obesity; or animal studies, were excluded unless they provided essential mechanistic data that would help to better understand the factors related to obesity that affect adolescent males.

In this study, title and abstract searches for relevance were done first on the eligible articles, then a full-text review was conducted of those articles that were eligible. Data was extracted from the articles for study design, population characteristics (age/gender), micronutrients being studied, prevalence estimates, mechanisms of action, and clinical consequences of reported findings as well as gaps in evidence regarding male adolescents.

All studies that reported sex-disaggregated findings, inflammatory mechanisms associated with obesity, and limitations of nutrition surveillance in LMIC's were of particular interest.

Since this was a scoping review that synthesized previous published literature, there were no direct participants or biological samples involved therefore there was no need for ethical approval from any institution for the use of human participants or the deposition of biological specimens with a specimen repository. All of the articles cited in this review can be obtained through their associated publishers/repositories using the appropriate Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

2. Pathophysiological Basis of Micronutrient Deficiency in Adolescent Obesity

Obesity among adolescents is a paradoxical form of "hidden hunger" in which there is an excess of calories but quality of micronutrients deficiencies [13]. Obese adolescents tend to eat an "obesogenic" diet that consists of many calories but high in fat and low in fibre [16]. Among the daily caloric intake in adolescents aged 11-18 years, ultra-processed foods account for 25.2% of their calorie intake, and there is a negative correlation between the amount of ultra-processed foods consumed and the amount of micronutrients consumed (protein, fibre, iron, calcium and zinc) [17]. The consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages (SSB) has also been shown to increase metabolic risk in this population because consumption of SSBs is associated with increased HOMA IR (a measure of insulin resistance) in this age group [18]. With only 23.5% of adolescents who are overweight or obese consuming sufficient daily servings of vegetables, the intake of fruits does not replace the poorer overall quality of diet [19]. This type of calorie-rich and nutrient-poor food intake supports the "hidden hunger" phenomenon, which

means that individuals have excess energy but not sufficient micronutrients in their diets [20]. Despite the evidence that ultra-processed foods are associated with obesity in this age group, it remains unclear due to the variation of results across different research studies [21]. Collectively, these types of dietary behaviours and eating patterns create a pathophysiologic paradox by being overnourished with corresponding micronutrient inadequacy.

Chronic low-grade inflammation is the result of poor functioning adipose tissue (fat) which produces a high amount of pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-6 (interleukin-6) and TNF- α (tumor necrosis factor-alpha) [22]. One-third of all IL-6 in the bloodstream comes directly from excess adipose (fat) tissue with a strong positive correlation to BMI SD scores [23]. The systemic inflammatory environment contributes to the pathological upregulation of hepcidin which is the master regulator of iron homeostasis primarily through IL-6 stimulating signaling pathways [24]. Increased hepcidin binds with ferroportin at the surface of cells causing its internal degradation and withholding iron from storage areas such as macrophages [23]. Hypernutrition results in a continual excess of substrate (food) placed on the mitochondria of adipocytes (fat cells); this overload decreases the efficiency of the mitochondria's electron transport chain resulting in increased amounts of unpaired electrons leaking from the chain and producing excessive amounts of reactive oxygen species [25]. The oxidative distress created results in an increased depletion of essential micronutrient co-factors such as zinc and selenium; leading to an increased depletion of the body's antioxidant reserve [23]. Obesity-related inflammation disrupts multiple micronutrient pathways providing the basis for the paradox known as "hidden hunger" as one has an abundance of energy and a concurrent deficit of micronutrients.

Adipose tissue functions as a volumetric reservoir for the storage of vitamin D, resulting in low circulating levels of 25-hydroxyvitamin D [26]. Meta-analyses have demonstrated that pediatric obesity increases the odds of having a vitamin D deficiency by a relative risk of 1.41 (95% CI: 1.26-to-1.59) [27]. Pro-inflammatory cytokines inhibit the activating enzyme CYP27B1 and enhance the expression of the degradative enzyme CYP24A1 in adipocytes, thereby reducing local levels of bioactive vitamin D further [26]. Due to these effects, children and adolescents with obesity require 2-to-3 times the standard vitamin D dosing regimen in order to achieve a serum concentration of 30 ng/mL [28]. In addition, obesity affects adipokine levels in children and adolescents; children and adolescents with insulin resistance have lower levels of circulating adiponectin and higher levels of leptin compared to their normal-weight peers [29]. The combination of these effects with poor gastrointestinal absorption and changes

in drug distribution decreases the bioavailability of iron, zinc, magnesium, and vitamin B12 [30]. Vitamin D deficiency further promotes adipogenesis and leptin resistance, which continues through a cycle of metabolic dysfunction [28].

Adolescents who do not eat breakfast often (0-2 days per week) have a much greater chance of being overweight or obese than adolescents who eat breakfast on a regular basis (each day) (OR=2.05 95% CI=1.61-2.61). They are also much more likely to have anaemia (OR=2.85; 95% CI=1.71-4.76) than those eating breakfast regularly [31]. Adolescents who skip breakfast also tend to have poor overall dietary quality [32]. In addition, sedentary behaviour increases the diet-related risk of adolescents since 75% of them participate in sedentary activities and more than 80% do not consume an adequate amount of fruit and vegetables daily [33]. Screen time has been shown to be a predictor of higher consumption of ultra-processed food items [34]. Lastly, fewer than half of adolescents are achieving the recommended level of physical fitness [35]. Restricting caloric intake can also lead to a greater number of adolescents with deficits in micronutrients, as many adolescents with restrictive eating behaviours meet only 20-30% of the recommended level for multiple vitamins and minerals [36]. Therefore, these behavioural patterns including meal skipping, excessive screen time, lack of physical activity, and restrictive eating are thus contributing factors to the paradox of consuming excessive numbers of calories while experiencing concurrent micronutrient deficiencies.

3. Major Micronutrient Deficiencies in Adolescents with Obesity

3.1 Vitamin D Deficiency

Adiposity in adolescent obesity results in a larger fat mass and associated reduction in circulation levels of vitamin D metabolites [26]. Based on a meta-analysis of 24,600 adolescents and children with obesity, the relative risk for vitamin D deficiency is 1.41 (95% CI: 1.26 - 1.59) [27]. Additionally, the moderate to strong inverse correlation of vitamin D levels with obesity ($r = -0.299$; $p < 0.01$) suggests an increased likelihood of deficient vitamin D levels in adolescents with obesity, with odds reaching 2.6 (95% CI: 1.4 - 4.76) for experiencing vitamin D deficiency [37]. Furthermore, the severity of obesity increases the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency, with 71.5 percent of severely obese adolescents having levels less than 30 ng/mL and having serum levels that are inversely correlated with BMI ($r = -0.31$; $p = 0.015$) [38]. Mechanistically, the inflammation associated with adipose tissue through TNF α and IL 6 down-regulates the enzyme CYP27B1 that activates vitamin D and

up-regulates the enzyme CYP24A1 that degrades vitamin D metabolite, creating a "double hit" to local levels of 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D and impeding vitamin D receptor signaling [26]. Finally, alterations in vitamin D binding protein secondary to obesity reduce the bioavailable or free vitamin D metabolite fraction and create tissue vitamin D deficiency even when total serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels are borderline [26]. Obese children with a deficiency of Vitamin D also are impacted by their adipose tissue endocrine system. A clinical MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) study showed that overweight children with Vitamin D deficiency have lower levels of adiponectin (7.21 ± 1.64 versus similar children without a vitamin D deficiency) and have much higher triglyceride levels (171.31 ± 80.75 mg/dL) [39]. Therefore, the standard serum value of 25(OH)D is an under-representation of a functional deficiency, and that a lower level of vitamin D will exacerbate metabolic dysregulation and insulin resistance [26;37].

3.2 Iron and Zinc Deficiency

Adolescent obesity is associated with increased risk for iron deficiency. A meta-analysis of 16 studies (n = 20 949) finds a pooled odds ratio (OR) for iron deficiency in obese children of 1.64 (95 % confidence interval [CI]: 1.22–2.21), with an overall prevalence of 20.07 % [40]. Another larger meta-analysis (n = 190 443) with data from 44 separate countries supports the increased odds of iron deficiency resulting from being overweight/obese (OR = 1.51, 95 % CI: 1.20–1.82), and even higher (OR = 1.88, 95 % CI: 1.33–2.43) for obesity alone [41]. The underlying mechanism for defective iron metabolism in obesity is primarily the activation of hepcidin by chronic inflammation due to excess adipose tissue, which in turn reduces serum iron and transferrin saturation while increasing ferritin, thereby demonstrating functional iron sequestration [40]. The fact that obesity-related chronic inflammation leads to low serum iron levels, even though many obese adolescents may have normal/high total body iron (as measured by ferritin), ultimately explains why obese adolescents typically have low levels circulating iron but often normal high levels of ferritin [40]. Clinically, 50 % of overweight children have iron deficiency and 38.5 % have iron deficiency anemia [38]. Adipose tissue also contributes directly to this chronic inflammatory state, which negatively impacts iron absorption and recycling [38].

Zinc deficiency is frequently encountered amongst adolescents with obesity. Studies have shown that Mexican children with overweight or obesity had a significantly increased risk of zinc deficiency [42]. In a national study conducted in China on 64 850 children, an overall zinc

deficiency prevalence of 9.62% was determined and that male children were at a higher risk of developing zinc deficiency than females [43]. The results of numerous studies have shown that overweight and obese children had significantly lower serum zinc levels than those of a normal weight, suggesting alterations in zinc metabolism and bioavailability are associated with obesity [29]. In addition, serum zinc levels have positive correlation with insulin resistance markers (higher HOMA IR and fasting glucose), which indicates a direct metabolic relationship [44]. Zinc metabolism is altered in adolescents with obesity due to oxidative stress and systemic inflammation. A reduction in oxidative stress and systemic inflammation occurs in obese adolescents following dietary intervention as evidenced by an increase in plasma zinc concentrations following dietary intervention [45]. The copper to zinc ratio is altered in obesity and may be indicative of trace element dysregulation ([45]. Children who are overweight or obese have altered metabolism of all the trace elements (iron, zinc, copper, manganese, and selenium) involved in redox homeostasis [46]. In summary, zinc deficiency and iron deficiency represent two components of hidden hunger in adolescents with obesity. Inflammation, altered absorption, and increased metabolic demands lead to both trace element deficiencies in this population.

3.3 Folate and Vitamin B12 Deficiency

In an analysis of 20 trials involving 7,791 adolescent participants, there was no observed variance in the serum concentrations of vitamins B12 and folate between overweight and normal weight subjects (SMD: -0.24, 95% CI: -0.53 to 0.06) (SMD: -0.12, 95% CI: -0.29 to 0.06) [47]. However, obese adolescents had significantly higher homocysteine (Hcy) levels than non-obese adolescents (SMD: 0.77, 95% CI: 0.39 to 1.14; $p < 0.001$), thereby indicating a potential association between homocysteine and the development of obesity [47]. Hyperhomocysteinemia was present in 27.5% of adolescents who are overweight, and serum Hcy was negatively correlated to both vitamin B12 and folate ($p \leq 0.05$) [48]. Folate deficiency was significantly more common in those with hyperhomocysteinemia than in those without (33.3% vs. 6.7%; OR = 6.82; 95% CI: 1.80 to 29.37; $p = 0.002$) [47]. In a population-based study of 1,520 adolescent girls, 32.1% were found to have vitamin B12 deficiency, while 11.8% exhibited folate deficiency [49]. Of the girls with low serum B12, poor secretion of insulin was occurring [49]. Additionally, low serum B12 has been correlated to a poorer metabolic phenotype (in other words, increased glucose intolerance and increased lipogenesis) [50]. A large national survey of more than 112,000 children showed that low serum folate levels were independently predictive of an increased likelihood of developing future childhood

obesity/metabolic syndrome [51]. In youth with obesity and metabolic syndrome, significantly reduced vitamin B12 and folic acid levels exist compared to non-obese children [52]. The underlying problems causing these vitamin deficiencies are; low diet quality, greater metabolic demands and compromised absorption (due to factors such as inflammation, etc.) [20]. The result is that folate and vitamin B12 deficiencies contribute to “hidden hunger” in adolescent obesity, while increased homocysteine levels create a direct link between micronutrient levels and metabolic dysfunction.

Table 1: Major micronutrient deficiencies in adolescents with obesity

Micronutrient	Prevalence / Quantitative data	Key mechanisms in obesity	Clinical consequences	Key references
Vitamin D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RR for deficiency: 1.41 (95% CI:1.26–1.59) • Pooled OR for deficiency: 2.6 (95% CI: 1.4–4.76) • Up to 71.5% in severe obesity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adipose tissue volumetric sink • TNF-α/IL-6 down-regulate CYP27B1, up-regulate CYP24A1 (“double hit”) • Altered vitamin D-binding protein reduces free fraction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insulin resistance • Lower adiponectin, higher triglycerides • Impaired bone mineralization 	
Iron	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pooled OR for deficiency: 1.64 (95% CI: 1.22–2.21) • Pooled prevalence: 20.07% • 50% in overweight children 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hepcidin upregulation by IL-6 • Ferroportin internalisation → iron sequestration • Functional iron deficiency with normal/high ferritin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatigue, reduced exercise capacity • Impaired cognitive function • Impaired thermoregulation 	

Zinc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence 9.62% in Chinese cohort • Overweight/obese children have significantly lower serum zinc • Obesity associated with higher risk of zinc deficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased urinary excretion • Inflammatory cytokine interference with absorption • Oxidative stress increases demand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impaired immune function • Reduced testosterone synthesis in males • Insulin resistance 	
Folate & Vitamin B12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B12 deficiency 32.1%, folate deficiency 11.8% in adolescent girls • Hyperhomocysteinemia in 27.5% of obese adolescents • OR for folate deficiency with hyperhomocysteinemia: 6.82 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor diet quality (low green vegetables, animal proteins) • Folate deficiency independently predicts hyperhomocysteinemia • Obesity-associated malabsorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elevated homocysteine → cardiovascular risk • Poor insulin secretion • Fatigue, megaloblastic anaemia 	

4. Male Adolescents as an Underrecognized Nutritional Risk Group

The existence of gender disparity with regard to male adolescent nutrition research is largely due to the longstanding trend of focusing primarily on women's health. There are many barriers that have prevented researchers from assessing the nutritional risks of male adolescents, as illustrated by Demmler et al. (2023), who found that sex-disaggregated dietary data are virtually nonexistent globally, thereby limiting the ability to assess the nutritional risks of boys [15]. Even though boys and girls have different biological and thus different nutritional requirements during adolescence, very few (if any) nutrition interventions target specific needs of boys [14]. In particular, 57% of community-based nutrition programs in LMIC (low and middle-income) countries are exclusively targeted at girls and completely dismiss boys [53]. This focus on girls stems from an established policy agenda that aims to improve the nutritional status of adolescent girls, which has unintentionally created an assumption that boys have less risk of malnutrition. Therefore, one of the most overlooked groups of malnourished individuals globally are male adolescents.

4.1 Potential Biological, Behavioral and Sociocultural Factors Contributing to Nutritional Vulnerability in Boys

Although boys and girls experience the same amount of severely deficient diet, boys on average have more wasted, stunted and underweight bodies than girls [54]. Boys are biologically at a greater risk for becoming zinc deficient than girls, with a national prevalence of zinc deficiency of 9.62% in China in 64,850 children [43]. Males consistently consume fewer fruits, vegetables and whole grains than females while consuming more meat and poultry [55]. As a result, the quality of boys' diets is lower in general than that of girls, having less fibre per 100 kcal, a higher glycaemic load, and lower micronutrient density [55]. Males also have greater protein and energy needs than females during periods of growth and development associated with puberty, but boys often do not meet those high needs due to poor dietary patterns [14].

In terms of behaviours, 75% of adolescents participate in sedentary behaviours and 65.8% exceed 2 hours of daily screen time, while more than 80% of adolescents consume less than the recommended amounts of fruits and vegetables per day [33]. Higher BMIs are associated with being male, as 15.2% of males are overweight or obese versus 8.7% of females [33]. Sedentary behaviour and screen time displace and reduce the amount of time available for physical activity and encourage the consumption of energy-dense, nutrient-poor foods; thus, increasing the severity of micronutrient deficiencies in the younger population.

There are limited sources of socioculturally disaggregated global databases, making it difficult to demonstrate the extent to which boys face nutritional risk [15]. Both low and middle-income countries typically show inadequate intake of iron, zinc, calcium, and a number of vitamins for adolescent males. In addition, adolescent boys generally consume a lot of fast food and beverages that contain sugar. Although the obesity/metabolic syndrome phenomenon is much more common among adolescent males, they have significantly lower levels of vitamin B12 and folic acid than healthy adolescents and exhibit elevated HOMA IR, indicating insulin resistance [52]. Furthermore, there are many sociocultural factors that contribute to boys' nutritional needs, with many sociocultural practices and norms prioritising girls' reproductive health at the expense of boys' unique growth requirements [14]. Therefore, all of these factors combined make adolescent boys an under recognised group which faces nutritional risk.

4.2 Persistent Evidence Gaps and the Clinical Consequences of Underrecognized Micronutrient Deficiencies in Male Adolescents

There are very few long-term randomised trials aimed at male adolescents; even if there is a male targeted trial, there is usually no long term follow up data [57] about adequate nutrient intake for boys' diet, and there are no established guidelines or threshold amounts of food groupings to determine whether or not they have adequate micronutrients [58]. In addition, there are very few longitudinal studies that track changes in nutrient intake throughout male adolescence with the CRO PALS study being a rare example [59]. Additionally, there is a lack of research on the implementation of interventions in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), and few data from surveillance systems for boys are available due to the fact that those systems tend not to collect sex disaggregated data [60]. There is no agreement on the best nutritional screening tools for adolescents and no established set of uniform nutritional screening recommendations for adolescent males [61]. Consequently, there are direct clinical implications associated with these knowledge gaps. The impact of poor nutrition during adolescence causes immediate micronutrient deficiencies and, over the long term, poses increased risk for overweight and obesity and cardiometabolic disease [5]. In one sample of adolescent males, iron deficiency (ID), anaemia and low vitamin B12 before the age range of 12 years were found to be statistically significantly associated with an increase in mean externalising behaviour problem scores for those males by 5.9 (95% CI: 1;0, 10.7), 6.6 (95% CI: 1.9, 11.3) and 2.7 (95% CI: 0.4, 4.9) units respectively, and none of the females in that study demonstrated such mean behaviour problem scores [62]. The existing lack of tracking male-specific nutritional statistics means that the sex-specific developmental effects – namely,

behaviour, cognitive and metabolic problems – remain unrecognised and unaddressed [62; 5]. The persistent lack of standard screening protocols or male-inclusive intervention trials will permit the ‘invisible burden’ of micronutrient deficits in adolescent males to continue into adulthood and thus perpetuate significant disparities in long-term health outcomes.

Table 2. Sex-specific nutritional vulnerabilities and evidence limitations in male adolescents

Vulnerability / limitation	Evidence / quantitative data	References
Biological vulnerability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boys more likely to be wasted, stunted, underweight; sex differences most pronounced in severe undernutrition [54]. • Higher zinc deficiency risk in males (prevalence 9.62%) [43]. • Male sex associated with lower fruit, vegetable, whole grain intake and poorer diet quality (less fibre, higher glycaemic load) [55]. • Higher protein/energy requirements during puberty often unmet [14]. 	[54;43;55;14].
Behavioural vulnerability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 75% of adolescents engage in sedentary behaviours; 65.8% have >2 h/day screen time; >80% fail fruit/vegetable recommendations [33]. • Increased BMI significantly associated with 	[33; 56].

	<p>being a boy (15.2% boys' overweight/obese vs. 8.7% girls) [33].</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In LMICs, inadequate intake of iron, zinc, calcium, multiple vitamins with high fast-food/soft drink consumption [56]. 	
Lack of sex-disaggregated data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Globally, sex-disaggregated dietary data scarce, limiting assessment of boys' nutritional risks [15]. • Over one-third of countries have no adolescent dietary data; 14% lack nationally representative surveys [15]. 	[15].
Lack of male-focused interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 57% of community-based nutrition programs in LMICs target only girls, explicitly excluding boys [53]. • Most interventions not designed for male-specific requirements [14]. 	[53;14].
Absence of validated screening thresholds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated food group thresholds for predicting micronutrient adequacy unavailable for boys [58] • No consensus on optimal nutritional screening tools; standardised screening recommendations absent for male populations [61]. 	[58;61].

Clinical consequences of neglect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iron deficiency, anaemia, low vitamin B-12 in middle childhood associated with externalising behaviour problems in adolescent boys (5.9, 6.6, 2.7 units higher scores, respectively); no associations in girls [62]. • Poor adolescent nutrition leads to immediate micronutrient deficiencies and long-term cardiometabolic risk [5]. 	[62;5].
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5. Other Understudied Adolescent Populations: Adolescent Athletes and Adolescents Undergoing Bariatric Surgery

Adolescents who are athletes do not always have the required amount of energy and carbohydrate, thus putting them at risk of not getting enough micronutrients during critical growth periods [63]. Young athletes have an estimated 20 percent chance of suffering from iron deficiency, which has an independent association with reduced peak oxygen consumption (response odds ratio - 0.94, 95 percent confidence intervals - 0.91 - 0.97) and a substantially lower probability of obtaining a high level of fitness [64]. The prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among elite adolescent athletes is 39 percent (95 percent confidence intervals - 25 - 55 percent), significantly higher than the 30 percent prevalence rate in adults [65]. Athletes of this age group do not have an adequate knowledge base regarding dietary supplements and are therefore at greater risk for inappropriate supplementation and imbalance of nutrients [66]. Young endurance athletes are at very high risk for RED-S and, as a consequence, need to have their nutritional status and dietary intake monitored on an ongoing basis because of the direct impact that RED-S can have on nutrition status.

The group of adolescents going through bariatric surgery are an extremely under studied group of patients. The published meta-analysis of 5 studies reported the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency at 41%, the prevalence of low ferritin at 49%, the prevalence of iron deficiency was

23%, the prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency was 20%, and the prevalence of calcium deficiency at 10% post-operatively [67]. There is long term prospective (10 year) follow up data indicating deficiencies worsen with time; the prevalence of iron deficiency increased from 9.0% to 18.7% ($P < 0.05$), the prevalence of folic acid deficiency increased from 1.3% to 11.6% ($P < 0.001$) and the prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency increased from 7.1% to 17.4% ($P < 0.01$) [68]. Different surgical procedures produce different long-term effects on iron metabolism; gastric bypass leads to decreased serum iron levels and sleeve gastrectomy results in decreases in total iron binding capacity [68]. Additionally, the Teen LABS 10 year follow up cohort showed no change in prevalence of obesity-related co-morbidities, including persistent micronutrient deficiencies after the insertion of laparoscopic adjustable gastric bands [69]. These findings demonstrate an urgent need for routine, life-long nutritional monitoring and procedure-specific and sex-specific screening protocols for both adolescent athletes and adolescents undergoing bariatric surgery.

6. Clinical and Public Health Implications

Every overweight or obese adolescent should have a thorough metabolic evaluation, including routine laboratory tests, as Body Mass Index, on its own, is not a reliable way to discover metabolic predisposition [70]. Some suggested indicators of metabolic predisposition are waist-to-height and skinfold thickness ratios, and lipids [70]. Weight loss should not be the only focus of obesity (co-morbid major health problem) management. Obesity management should also include a focus on micronutrient deficiency or insufficiency, as evidence shows that thiamine intake is positively associated with obesity and selenium intake is negatively associated with obesity in an analysis of a cohort of 3529 children. Vitamin D, riboflavin, calcium, copper, iron, phosphorus, potassium and vitamin E intakes were also negatively associated with acanthosis nigricans, a sign of insulin resistance [71]. This indicates that micronutrient deficiencies are common in adolescents with obesity, and therefore, a targeted approach to dietary management that addresses the individual needs for micronutrients would also help with weight control.

Sensitive to the differences between male and female adolescents, the assessment of their nutritional status is necessary to enable them to achieve adequate levels of nutrients [14]. Accurate nutritional assessment will require the use of precision medicine approaches that take into consideration sex-based biological and sociocultural differences [14].

Interventions in schools for adolescents can be an excellent source of improving the nutrition of adolescent students [70]. However, very few studies have documented gender specific outcomes from these types of programmes. Further research needs to develop, implement and assess interventions that promote food behaviours among both genders and include gender disaggregated data.

For evidence-based initiatives to support public health outcomes, improved surveillance activities are needed to understand adolescent dietary behaviours. A systematic scoping review of 722 articles and 1223 datasets conducted on adolescent nutritional information from around the world found that one-third of all countries do not have any dietary information for adolescents and fourteen percent of all countries do not have any representative surveys on adolescent eating patterns [15]. The majority of these data deficient countries are located in sub-Saharan Africa, Europe, and Central Asia [15]. The need for improving surveillance through routine micronutrient screening, sex-sensitive assessments, inclusive school-based interventions, and building nationally representative dietary data systems is vital for reducing the hidden hunger associated with obesity among male and female adolescents.

7. Future Research Directions and Conclusion

To address hidden hunger among adolescents globally, future research needs to focus on implementation science to understand the most effective ways to implement micronutrient interventions at scale, across various delivery methods that include both school-based and home-based approaches as well as both in-person and digital. Furthermore, high-quality nationally representative data on micronutrient status for adolescents and the incidence of multiple micronutrient deficiencies is needed in all geographic regions of the world as well as low- and middle-income countries, which have larger gaps in surveillance. In addition, we need mechanistic research that goes beyond cross-sectional associations to establish causal pathways from specific micronutrients (e.g., iron, zinc, vitamin D, B vitamins) to mental health (e.g., depression, anxiety, cognitive functioning), using longitudinal research and randomised controlled trials. Identifying these gaps will enable the development of evidence based, sex sensitive and scalable nutritional interventions that can be reliably implemented to reduce the global burden of hidden hunger in adolescents.

Adolescent obesity has created a huge amount of hidden hunger as a public health crisis because of metabolic problems, inflammatory processes, and poor nutritional quality. Unfortunately, male adolescents have a distinct vulnerability to obesity, but there has been little

research done on them regarding their nutrition. Routine screening for micronutrients, utilizing sex-specific treatments, and developing better tracking systems will help prevent long-term problems relating to metabolism, cognition and development.

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Conflict of interest

Author declares no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

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